

Thin Layer Chromatographic Analysis of Some Mercaptoacetamides

K. K. JAIN, S. BATEJA and C. S. BHANDARI

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004

Manuscript received 16 May 1980, accepted 28 September 1982

Thin layer chromatographic studies of N-aryl substituted-2-mercapto acetamides have been made using different solvent systems. R_f values increase regularly with the increase in dielectric constant of the solvent in the order $\text{CHCl}_3 > \text{CH}_2\text{COCH}_3 > \text{CH}_2\text{OH} > \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$.

CHROMATOGRAPHIC studies of N-phenyl-2-mercaptoacetamide and its analogues have not been reported in literature. The present paper reports a method for the separation and detection of N-aryl mono substituted-2-mercaptoacetamides in microgram quantities on thin layer silica gel G using non-aqueous solvent systems.

Experimental

Apparatus and reagent: Standard Biochem TLC kit, supplied by Universal Biochemicals, Madurai, was used in running the chromatograms. All chemicals used were of analytical grade or purified by distillation as such or under reduced pressure.

Preparation: N-Aryl mono substituted mercaptoacetamides were prepared by the method described earlier^{1,2}. Their disulphides, $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHC(O)CH}_2\text{S})_2$, were prepared by the oxidation of corresponding mercaptoacetamides with iodine in aqueous-alcoholic solution.

where $\text{R} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_4(-p\text{-X})$; where $\text{X} = \text{H}$ or Cl) NHC(O)CH_2 . The crude was filtered and purified by crystallisation.

Chromatographic procedure: Five plates (200 × 200 mm) coated uniformly with silica gel G (30 g/60 ml water; thickness of the layer 250 μ) were air dried, activated by heating in an oven at 120° for 1 hr and cooled to room temperature (30°) before use. Alcoholic solution of the compounds (1-10 μg/ml) was used in spotting the spots on the plates with a micropipette. The spots were 10 mm apart and the size of a single spot was less than 3 mm in diam. These plates were placed in a developing tank saturated with the solvent and developed by ascending method until the solvent front had travelled 100-150 mm. After marking the solvent front the plates were allowed to dry. The spots were identified in brown colour on exposing the plates to iodine vapour. The mean

R_f value for N-phenyl-2-mercaptoacetamide (compound 1; Table 1), taken as reference or standard, was obtained from three plates with six spots each. This mean value was regarded as fixed. The mean R_f values of all compounds were obtained from three plates with six spots each. N-Phenyl-2-mercaptoacetamide was included on all plates as a standard. Relative R_f values were thus obtained and corrected in terms of fixed value of the standard. R_f values were reproducible within ±0.02 R_f unit.

Results and Discussion

Out of the various solvent combinations studied the following were found to be most suitable:

- benzene, chloroform and glacial acetic acid (85 : 10 : 5),
- benzene, acetone and glacial acetic acid (85 : 10 : 5),
- benzene, isopropanol and glacial acetic acid (85 : 10 : 5), and
- benzene, methanol and glacial acetic acid (85 : 10 : 5).

Solvent systems without acetic acid did not yield good separation either due to trailing of the spots in some cases or to low R_f values. The disulphides (compounds No. 1 and 2; Table 2) had lower R_f values in comparison to the corresponding mercaptoacetamides (Table 1). This is possibly due to the fact that disulphide molecules are bulkier than simple mercaptoacetamides molecules. It was noticed that by changing the solvent in which mercaptoacetamides were soluble, the R_f values increased regularly with the increase in the dielectric constant of the solvent in the order chloroform > acetone > isopropanol > methanol.

Effect of substitution on R_f values: Substitution of an electron withdrawing group in *para* or *meta* position of the phenyl ring, such as NO_2 , decreases the R_f values. Conversely, an electron releasing

TABLE 1—THIN LAYER CHROMATOGRAPHIC DATA FOR MERCAPTOACETAMIDES (R-NHCOCH₂SH)

Sl. No.	Compound R	System A		System B		System C		System D	
		hR _f	hR _{st}						
1.	C ₆ H ₅	30	100	52	100	55	100	64	100
2.	C ₆ H ₄ (<i>p</i> -F)	27	90	52	100	56	102	63	98
3.	C ₆ H ₄ (<i>p</i> -Cl)	30	100	49	94	51	93	62	97
4.	C ₆ H ₄ (<i>p</i> -Br)	33	110	52.5	101	57	107	62	97
5.	C ₆ H ₄ (<i>p</i> -I)	35	117	51	98	55	100	60	94
6.	C ₆ H ₄ (<i>p</i> -NO ₂)	21	70	47	90	49	90	57	89
7.	C ₆ H ₄ (<i>p</i> -OH ₃)	31	103	54	104	57	104	66	103
8.	C ₆ H ₄ (<i>m</i> -Cl)	33	110	52	100	57	104	65	102
9.	C ₆ H ₄ (<i>m</i> -NO ₂)	23	77	48	92	51	93	58	91
10.	C ₆ H ₄ (<i>m</i> -CH ₃)	30	100	51	98	56	102	63	98
11.	C ₆ H ₄ (<i>o</i> -Cl)	40	133	70	135	70	127	76	119
12.	C ₆ H ₄ (<i>o</i> -CH ₃)	—	—	48	92	52	95	61	95
13.	C ₆ H ₄ (<i>o</i> -OCH ₃)	38	127	62	119	63	115	74	116

Solvent system A : Benzene, chloroform and glacial acetic acid (85 : 10 : 5)

Solvent system B : Benzene, acetone and glacial acetic acid (85 : 10 : 5)

Solvent system C : Benzene, isopropanol and glacial acetic acid (85 : 10 : 5)

Solvent system D : Benzene, methanol and glacial acetic acid (85 : 10 : 5)

TABLE 2—THIN LAYER CHROMATOGRAPHIC DATA FOR DISULPHIDES

Compound	System A*		System B		System C		System D	
	hR _f	hR _{st}						
1. (C ₆ H ₅ NHCOCH ₂ S) ₂	13	43	14	27	14	26	16	25
2. [C ₆ H ₄ (<i>p</i> -Cl)-NHCOCH ₂ S] ₂	13	43	15	29	15	27	18	28

*Solvent systems are the same as in Table 1.

group such as CH₃, causes an increase in R_f values. Effect of halogen substitution is not clearly understood in terms of electromeric effect. However, R_f values increase in the order F > Cl > Br > I in solvent A system (Table 1). The substitution of Cl, OCH₃ or CH₃ group in *ortho* position of the phenyl ring causes an increase in R_f value in comparison to compound 1 possibly due to +M effect of Cl or OCH₃ group.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Head of the Chemistry Department for facilities. (S. B.) and

(K. K. J.) are also thankful to C. S. I. R., New Delhi and University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, respectively for Research Fellowships.

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